

Human Motion Prediction using Interacting Multiple Model Filtering enhanced by a Kinematic Model

Michele Ferrari*[†] and Manuel Beschi*[†]

* Dipartimento di Ingegneria Meccanica e Industriale, University of Brescia, Italy

[†]Institute of Intelligent Industrial Technologies and Systems for Advanced Manufacturing, National Research Council of Italy
 Corresponding author: Michele Ferrari (michele.ferrari@unibs.it)

Abstract—Predicting human motion enhances safety and efficiency in human–robot collaboration. We evaluate a predictor based on an Interacting Multiple Model (IMM) estimator combined with a human dynamics and control model. This approach is compared against a baseline Unscented Kalman Filter (UKF) using a constant acceleration model (CA). Additionally, we introduce a human kinematic model to predict joint angles instead of keypoints, enforcing kinematic constraints.

Index Terms—Human-motion prediction, Safe human-robot interaction, Unscented Kalman Filter

I. INTRODUCTION

In human–robot collaboration, predicting human motion enables the design of safe robot trajectories (per ISO/TS 15066:2016 [1]), allowing path and task adjustments to prevent collisions, avoid unnecessary stops, and anticipate human actions. Prior methods for human pose prediction include Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) [2], Inverse Optimal Control [3], graphical models such as Hidden Markov Models (HMMs) [4], and other learning-based techniques [5]. We propose instead a pose prediction method based on an Interacting Multiple Model (IMM) estimator [6] and a simplified human motion model suited for scenarios with minimal tracking data.

II. METHOD

A. Problem definition

The human position is defined as the set of n body key points $p_i \in \mathbb{R}^3$ in Cartesian space: $y \in \mathbb{R}^{3n} = [p_1^T, p_2^T, \dots, p_n^T]^T$. These key points can be readily obtained using vision-based skeleton tracking systems.

Following [7], we introduce a *human dynamic model* that describes body motion:

$$\begin{cases} y(t) = h_h(x_h(t)) \\ \dot{x}_h(t) = f_h(x_h(t), u(t)) \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where x_h is the dynamic state, u is the input signal, $f_h(\cdot)$ is the dynamic function, and $h_h(\cdot)$ is the output function.

We also define a *human control model* that computes the control signal $u(t)$ generated by the human and used by the dynamic model in (1):

$$\begin{cases} u(t) = h_c(x_h(t), x_c(t), r(t)) \\ \dot{x}_c(t) = f_c(x_h(t), x_c(t), r(t)) \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where x_c is the controller internal state, r is an exogenous signal (e.g., the target object position during grasping), $f_c(\cdot)$

Fig. 1: The skeletonized operator in the collaborative robotic cell.

is the controller dynamic function, and $h_c(\cdot)$ is the controller output function. The full dynamic model is obtained by combining and discretizing equations (1) and (2).

The state $x(k|k)$ and covariance $P(k|k)$ are estimated by a state observer. In the *predict* step, it computes $x(k+1|k)$ and $P(k+1|k)$ at the time $k+1$ based on information available at time k . In the *update* step, it corrects the estimate with the actual measurements computing $x(k|k)$ and $P(k|k)$. In this work, the *predict* step is iterated n times to compute the n -step-ahead prediction of the future position $y(k+n|k)$.

B. Predictor implementation

The most straightforward approach operates directly in the Cartesian space of human keypoints. In this case, the state vector is defined as $x_h(t) = [y(t)^T, v(t)^T]^T$, where $v(t) = \dot{y}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{3n}$ represents the human velocity. The dynamic system in (1) can then be modeled as a double integrator between acceleration u and position y .

A more sophisticated strategy defines the state vector as $x_h = [q_i]$, a set of joint variables q_i for $i \in [1, \dots, n_{DoF}]$ that represent the human’s kinematic configuration. The state-transition model f_h remains a double integrator, now applied to joint acceleration and position. Unlike the previous approach, the output function h_h involves computing the forward kinematics of the human model:

$$y(t) = f_{kin}(x_h(t)) \quad (3)$$

where the $f_{kin}(\cdot)$ is the nonlinear forward kinematics. In this work, we implement a 28-DoF kinematic model¹ (Fig. 2).

The *human control model* in (2) can be complex and nonlinear when exogenous information is available. However, when only pose tracking data is provided, it is possible to

¹https://github.com/JRL-CARI-CNR-UNIBS/human_kinematic_model.git

TABLE I: Performance Metrics computed on the Validation Set

Prediction Window	Model	REACH-TO-GRASP		WALKING		PASSING-BY	
		$\mu_e (\times 10^{-4} \text{ m})$	$\sigma_e (\times 10^{-2} \text{ m})$	$\mu_e (\times 10^{-4} \text{ m})$	$\sigma_e (\times 10^{-2} \text{ m})$	$\mu_e (\times 10^{-4} \text{ m})$	$\sigma_e (\times 10^{-2} \text{ m})$
0.1 s (one step)	CA	-1.79	1.06	-32.4	1.36	-55.4	1.64
	IMM	-1.46	0.78	-31.5	1.07	-54.5	1.38
0.3 s (three steps)	CA	0.530	3.25	-35.4	4.03	-112	7.33
	IMM	-2.37	2.64	-39.5	3.93	101	6.78
0.5 s (five steps)	CA	1.81	6.42	-40.2	7.86	-171	11.1
	IMM	-2.23	4.93	-43.3	6.72	-148	10.0

Fig. 2: The reference frames of the human kinematic model.

assume that the acceleration u is a piecewise constant function. In this case, (2) simplifies to $u(t) = 0$ when the velocity is constant, or

$$\begin{cases} u(t) = x_c \\ \dot{x}_c = 0 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

when the acceleration is constant. The Interacting Multiple Model (IMM) algorithm efficiently combines Unscented Kalman Filters based on constant acceleration (CA) and constant velocity (CV) control models. It handles transitions between these modes by updating their associated probabilities through a Markov chain.

III. SETUP AND EXPERIMENTS

Experiments were conducted in an industrial collaborative robotic cell using a StereoLabs ZED RGB-D camera. The camera runs proprietary skeletonization software at ~ 25 Hz to detect human key points. Ten subjects performed various tasks (e.g., reach-to-grasp, walking, passing-by) at different speeds. The study evaluated the predictive accuracy and uncertainty bounds of the proposed model under varying conditions.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Let $e(k) = y(k|k) - y(k|k-n)$ denote the keypoint-wise error between the current filter estimate and the n -step-ahead prediction. The following error metrics were evaluated:

- the **mean value** $\mu_e = \mathbb{E}(e)$ of the key-point-wise error. This metric verifies the assumption of estimator *mean-unbiasedness*. A lower μ_e indicates a less biased n -step-ahead prediction.
- the **standard deviation** $\sigma_e = \sqrt{\mathbb{E}[(e - \mu_e)(e - \mu_e)^T]}$ of the key-point-wise error. This value represents the

spread of the prediction error around its mean value and thus assesses the *accuracy* of the n -step estimate.

Table I reports the error metrics for each condition, aggregated by task-specific key points. Task velocity aggregation was also performed to derive a comprehensive global metric.

Overall, the mean error (μ_e) remains consistently low across tasks, indicating minimal bias in the predicted estimates. Although both the Constant Acceleration (CA) and Interacting Multiple Model (IMM) filters yield similar values for μ_e , the IMM shows a smaller standard deviation (σ_e), leading to reduced Root-Mean-Squared-Error (RMSE) across all tasks and prediction horizons.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

This study presents a human motion prediction framework based on sequential open-loop UKF prediction steps using a simple dynamic and control model, achieving reliable forecasts over a 0.5-second horizon. The Interacting Multiple Model (IMM) estimator effectively manages transitions between motion modalities without relying on complex, learned systems. Future work will aim to improve prediction accuracy by increasing the complexity of the *human control model*, potentially by learning typical control dynamics from data.

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